

FLEXURAL-TORSION COUPLING VIBRATION OF FIBER COMPOSITE BEAMS

Takehito Fukuda^{*1}, Kiwami Naito^{*2},
Mitsunori Miki^{*3} & Yoshihiko Sugiyama^{*3}

^{*1} Faculty of Engineering, Osaka City University

^{*2} Graduate School of Osaka City University

^{*3} College of Engineering, University of Osaka Prefecture

ABSTRACT

It is shown that the principal axis of elasticity (abbreviated to *PAE*) can be rotated from the structural axis by giving a specific fiber orientation or stacking sequence of a fiber composite beam. The theoretical results for *PAE* obtained by the use of the laminated plate theory agree with the experimental results for *PAE* of GFRP and CFRP laminated cantilever beams in the static flexural, torsional and flexural-torsion tests. It is illustrated by performing free vibration tests that even if a fiber composite beam has an eccentric mass, the torsional vibration can be prevented when *PAE* is made so as to go through the center of gravity by tailoring fiber orientations. The natural frequency of a beam is predicted by solving a simplified vibration equation of two degree-of-freedom system.

KEYWORDS: Fiber Composite Beam; Flexural-Torsion Coupling Vibration; Principal Axis of Elasticity (*PAE*); Fiber Orientation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Flexural-torsion vibration takes place in mechanical structures under dynamic loadings if the center of gravity of a member is off its principal axis of elasticity (abbreviated to *PAE*). In such cases, the flexural vibration can be restrained comparatively easily by using suitable vibration suppression devices, but the torsional vibration cannot be controlled so easily. For example, in operating a robot system, any disturbance produces robot arm vibration and especially torsional vibration decreases the operation efficiency and quality of the robot system. The improvement of oscillatory behavior of the robot system will be usually made by devising a mechanical and electrical control system.

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the prevention of torsional vibration under dynamic loadings by utilizing tailoring characteristics of composite materials from the viewpoint of

materials design. There are a lot of studies on anisotropy of composite materials¹⁾, but few investigations on flexural-torsion coupling vibration of composite laminates.^{2,3)} It is shown that *PAE* of fiber composite laminates can be designed so as to be on the center of gravity of the structure by choosing an appropriate fiber orientation or stacking sequence of laminate. It will be expected that this can make the prevention of torsional vibration of a mechanical structure.

2. PRINCIPAL AXIS OF ELASTICITY OF COMPOSITE BEAMS

2.1 Strain Energy of Composite Cantilever To explain *PAE* of a cantilever of composite materials, let us use a system of Cartesian coordinates as in Fig. 1. It shows a cantilever beam referred to a coordinate system. The origin is located at the fixed end and the *y* and *z*-axes coincide with the principal axes of inertia of the cross section and the *x*-axis coincides with the geometrical beam axis. *L* represents the length, *h*, the thickness and *B*, the width of a cantilever beam.

Here, the curvature along the *y*-axis and the in-plane strain at the midplane are negligible due to the geometry of the beam. Then the strain energy of a fiber composite laminate is given by

$$U = \int \int \int (\sigma_x \epsilon_x + \sigma_y \epsilon_y + \sigma_{xy} \epsilon_{xy}) dx dy dz . \quad (1)$$

The generalized Hook's law in terms of stiffness is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & Q_{16} \\ & Q_{22} & Q_{26} \\ S_{ym} & & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_{xy} \end{bmatrix} . \quad (2)$$

Thus Eq.(1) can be rewritten as follows:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int \int \int (Q_{11} \epsilon_x^2 + 2Q_{12} \epsilon_x \epsilon_y + 2Q_{16} \epsilon_x \epsilon_{xy} + 2Q_{26} \epsilon_y \epsilon_{xy} + Q_{22} \epsilon_y^2 + Q_{66} \epsilon_{xy}^2) dx dy dz . \quad (3)$$

In pure bending of symmetric laminates, Eq. (3) is reduced to Eq. (4) by using Kirchhoff's hypothesis.

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int \int \left[D_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + 2D_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + 4 \left(D_{16} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + D_{26} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} + 4D_{66} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 \right] dx dy , \quad (4)$$

where

$$D_{ij} = \int Q_{ij} z^2 dz . \quad (5)$$

For the curvature $k_y = 0$, we have

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int \int \left[D_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + 4D_{66} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 \right] dx dy . \quad (6)$$

2.2 Deformation of a Composite Cantilever Beam The deflection of a cantilever beam, $w(x,y)$, can be represented by

$$w(x,y) = \bar{w}(x) + y \theta(x) , \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{w}(x)$ is the deflection of a center line of the beam and $\theta(x)$ is the angle of torsion at x , respectively. Now we have the total strain energy of the beam as

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-B/2}^{B/2} \int_0^L (D_{11} w_{,xx}^2 + 4D_{16} w_{,xx} w_{,xy} + 4D_{66} w_{,xy}^2) dx dy , \quad (8)$$

where

$$w_{,xx} = \frac{d^2 \bar{w}(x)}{dx^2} + y \frac{d^2 \theta(x)}{dx^2} , \quad (9)$$

$$w_{,xy} = \frac{d\theta(x)}{dx} .$$

Here we approximate $\bar{w}(x)$ and $\theta(x)$ to the following polynomials;

$$\bar{w}(x) = a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + a_3 x^3 + a_4 x^4 , \quad (10)$$

$$\theta(x) = b_0 + b_1 x + b_2 x^2 + b_3 x^3 + b_4 x^4 .$$

For the boundary conditions $\bar{w}(x) = \theta(x) = d\bar{w}(x)/dx = 0$ and approximately $d\theta(x)/dx = 0$ at $x = 0$, we have $a_0 = b_0 = a_1 = b_1 = 0$. Thus we obtain

$$\bar{w}(x) = a_2 x^2 + a_3 x^3 + a_4 x^4 , \quad (11)$$

$$\theta(x) = b_2 x^2 + b_3 x^3 + b_4 x^4 .$$

Substituting these equations into Eq.(7) and evaluating the strain energy by Eq.(8), we have

$$U = 2BL \left(C_0 + \frac{1}{2} C_1 L + \frac{1}{3} C_2 L^2 + \frac{1}{4} C_3 L^3 + \frac{1}{5} C_4 L^4 + \frac{1}{6} C_5 L^5 + \frac{1}{7} C_6 L^6 \right) , \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C_0 &= D_{11} (a_2^2 + B^2 b_2^2 / 12) , \\ C_1 &= D_{11} (6a_2 a_3 + B^2 b_2 b_3 / 2) + 4D_{16} a_2 b_2 , \\ C_2 &= D_{11} (12a_2 a_4 + 9a_3^2 + 3B^2 b_2^2 / 4 + B^2 b_2 b_4) + 6D_{16} (a_2 b_3 + 2a_3 b_2) + 4D_{66} b_2^2 , \\ C_3 &= 3D_{11} (12a_3 a_4 + B^2 b_3 b_4) + D_{16} (18a_3 b_3 + 8a_2 b_4 + 24a_4 b_2) + 13D_{66} b_2 b_3 , \\ C_4 &= 3D_{11} (12a_4^2 + B^2 b_4^2) + 4D_{16} (9a_4 b_3 + 6a_3 b_4) + D_{66} (9b_3^2 + 16b_2 b_4) , \\ C_5 &= 48D_{16} a_4 b_4 + 24D_{66} b_3 b_4 , \\ C_6 &= 16D_{66} b_4^2 . \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

2.3 Potential Energy of External Forces When the load P and the torque T are applied at the free end of the cantilever, the potential energy of external forces is given by

$$V = P \delta_L + T \theta_L, \quad (14)$$

where δ_L and θ_L are the deflection and the torsional angle of the beam at the free end.

$$\delta_L = w(L) = a_2 L^2 + a_3 L^3 + a_4 L^4, \quad (15)$$

$$\theta_L = \theta(L) = b_2 L^2 + b_3 L^3 + b_4 L^4.$$

Thus we have the potential energy for external forces as:

$$V = P (a_2 L^2 + a_3 L^3 + a_4 L^4) + T (b_2 L^2 + b_3 L^3 + b_4 L^4). \quad (16)$$

Consequently, the total potential energy Ω is

$$\Omega = U - V. \quad (17)$$

Using the principle of minimum potential energy, we obtain the following equations:

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial a_i} = 0, \quad (i = 2, 3, 4) \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial b_i} = 0. \quad (i = 2, 3, 4)$$

These equations can be reduced to the simultaneous algebraic equations with regard to a_2, a_3, a_4, b_2, b_3 and b_4 . Solving them, we get six constants in Eq.(11). Once these constants are obtained, we can evaluate δ_L and θ_L in Eq.(15) and they are expressed as follows:

$$\delta_L = e_{11}P + e_{12}T, \quad (19)$$

$$\theta_L = e_{21}P + e_{22}T,$$

where e_{ij} are functions of components of the stiffness matrix and geometrical parameters of a fiber composite beam and the detail expressions are omitted since they are lengthy ones.

2.4 Analysis of Principal Axis of Elasticity (PAE) PAE is a symmetric axis with respect to elastic distortion and a load on the axis does not yield any torsion. Then we can put $T = P_0 L_e$ and $\theta_L = 0$ in Eq.(19). Thus we have

$$L_e = -\frac{e_{21}P}{e_{22}P_0}, \quad (20)$$

and angle η between the geometrical axis of a beam and PAE as shown in Fig. 1 is

$$\eta = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{e_{21}P}{e_{22}P_0 L} \right]. \quad (21)$$

3. EXPERIMENT

3.1 Specimens The specimens used in the present study were carbon fiber and glass fiber reinforced epoxy beams. Their elastic constants are shown in Table 1. For both fiber composites, two different types of stacking sequences were used in the analysis and experiments. One is symmetric angle-ply laminates whose fiber orientations are $\pm 30^\circ$, $\pm 45^\circ$ and $\pm 60^\circ$ and another is unidirectional laminates with fiber orientations of 30° , 45° and 60° . Test specimens with fiber orientations of 0° and 90° were also used. All of them were machined from 8-ply GFRP or CFRP panels. The beams were of the approximate dimensions of 25 mm wide by 1.2 mm for CFRP and 1.5 mm for GFRP thick and cantilever lengths of 200 mm for a symmetric angle-ply laminate and 100 mm for a unidirectional laminate.

3.2 Test Procedure In order to determine the direction of *PAE* of a cantilever, the static torsional tests were conducted for each specimen. The angles of torsion at the free end of a cantilever were measured by changing the position of an eccentric mass. Plotting the variation of them with the position of an eccentric mass as shown in Fig. 2, we obtained the distance L_e between the center of the free end and the position at which the torsional angle is zero on the graph. Thus angle η can be calculated by using the relation of $\tan^{-1}(L_e/L)$. Next, in free vibration tests, the initial deflections at the free end of the cantilever were constant for every test by giving the initial displacement at the fixed point as shown in Fig. 3. If the string that was fixed temporarily is burnt off with a lighter, the free vibration occurs.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, Fig. 4 shows the variation of angles of *PAE* with fiber orientation of ϕ . Four kinds of curves for the theoretical results were calculated by using Eq. (21). It is clear that the theoretical results agree with the experimental ones well. It is also illustrated that the stronger the anisotropy of laminates, the more largely *PAE* can be rotated. Next, test results of free vibration were obtained for the center of gravity on *PAE* in Fig. 5(a) and for 10 mm off *PAE* in Fig. 5(b). The former illustrates no torsional strain of a beam in the vibration and the latter shows the coupled flexural-torsion vibration of the beam. From these results, it is clear that no torsional vibration takes place when *PAE* is placed so as to be on the center of gravity even if there is an eccentric mass in the structure. Moreover, the natural frequencies were predicted by solving the vibration equation for a simplified model in which a cantilever beam involving an eccentric mass is regarded as a concentrated mass system of two degree-of-freedom. The comparisons of the calculated results with the experimental ones are shown in Figs. 6(a) and 6(b), where symbols \circ and \bullet mean GFRP laminates and symbols \ominus and \odot , CFRP laminates. Figure 6(a) is for symmetric angle-ply laminates of $\pm 30^\circ$ and Fig. 6(b), for unidirectional ones with fiber orientation of 30° . In both figures, the higher frequencies correspond to the torsional modes and the lower, the flexural modes. Calculated results agree with experimental ones fairly well.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Static and vibration tests were performed for cantilever beams of symmetric angle-ply and unidirectional laminates of GFRP and CFRP with several fiber orientations. The principal axis of elasticity (*PAE*) of the cantilever was defined as a symmetric axis with respect to elastic distortion on which a load yields no torsion. *PAE* was analyzed by the use of laminated plate theory and its result agreed with the experimental one. Torsional vibration of the cantilever was suppressed when the center of gravity of the system coincided with *PAE* determined by the static test. Natural frequencies of the cantilever were predicted by analyzing a simplified vibration model in which a cantilever with an eccentric mass was approximated to a concentrated mass system of two degree-of-freedom with regard to two variables of deflection and torsion. Calculated results of natural frequencies agreed with experimental ones fairly well.

6. REFERENCES

1. e.g., M. Miki and Y. Murotsu, Proc. of the Japan-US Conference on Composite Materials, Technomic Publishing Co., Lancaster, 1988, pp. 538-547.
2. R. B. Abarcar and P. F. Cunniff, Composite Materials J., **6** (6), 504 (1972).
3. R. D. Adams and D. G. C. Bacon, Composite Materials J., **7** (1), 53 (1973).

Fig. 1 Geometry and coordinates system of a fiber composite cantilever showing angle η of the principal axis of elasticity

Table 1 Elastic constants for GFRP and CFRP laminates

	E_x [GPa]	E_y [GPa]	E_s [GPa]	ν_x	ν_y
GFRP	49.3	19.3	5.80	0.26	0.11
CFRP	113	7.71	3.87	0.32	0.021

Fig. 2 Comparison of theoretical and experimental angles of torsion at the free end of the cantilever for various eccentricities

- ① Arm
- ② Eccentric Mass
- ③ Specimen
- ④ Scale
- ⑤ String
- ⑥ Temporary Fixed Point

Fig. 3 Instrument for free flexural-torsion vibration tests of the cantilever with an eccentric mass

Fig. 4 Variation of angles of PAE, η , with fiber orientation, ϕ , where symbol \circ is for symmetric GFRP, \bullet for unidirectional GFRP, \ominus for symmetric CFRP and \oplus for unidirectional CFRP laminates

Fig. 5(a) Free vibration responses of a symmetric laminated GFRP cantilever with fiber orientation of $\pm 30^\circ$ when an eccentric mass is on PAE

Fig. 5(b) Free vibration responses of a symmetric laminated GFRP cantilever with fiber orientation of $\pm 30^\circ$ when an eccentric mass is 10mm off PAE

Fig. 6(a) Comparison of theoretical and experimental results for natural frequencies of a symmetric $\pm 30^\circ$ angle-ply laminate as a function of eccentricity

Fig. 6(b) Comparison of theoretical and experimental results for natural frequencies of a unidirectional 30° laminate as a function of eccentricity